

Development of web-based student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

The Student Discipline Unit is responsible for carrying out and enforcing the policies, guidelines, rules, and regulations of St. Dominic College of Asia to maintain student decorum, peace, order, safety, and security. However, the procedures involved, such as recording violations committed by college students, maintaining records, and application of corresponding sanctions, are inconvenient and time-consuming. Information written on the violation slip form is not always a piece of substantial evidence since students may alter identities to avoid having violation records and punishments. All the collected filled violation slips are then manually inputted into Microsoft Excel for record-keeping; the Student Discipline Officer must go over each worksheet one by one to determine whether the student has committed an offense prior to signing the clearance. Violations committed inside the school are not observed or documented since offenses are only recorded at the main entrance and exit gates of the campus. As a result, the researchers created a web-based student violation management system based on the Laravel Framework as an alternative solution for the manual processing of recording offenses on and off-campus, managing records, and applying sanctions. The Agile Methodology was used to develop the system, which is part of the project's System Development Life Cycle. The system was evaluated using the ISO/IEC 9126 standard for software quality measurement to test the functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability of the system, with overall satisfaction, mean rate of 4.82 derived from the responses of eight respondents, the developed system is considered highly acceptable from the five-point category.

Keywords: *Student violation; Web-based system; Laravel Framework; Agile methodology; System Development Life Cycle.*

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Introduction

It is necessary to direct students to exhibit acceptable attitudes and behaviors within and outside the school. To achieve an organized and peaceful school environment and maintain law and order, school management specifies rules and regulations to guide the activities of members of the educational institution (Ndeto, 2015). The administration and faculty's job are to make sure that a school is a place of learning, largely free from distractions, and conducive to intellectual pursuits. The school is responsible for maintaining order, hence the limits on speech, dress, and behavior. There are consequences for what you do in the real world. Students must be instructed on proper conduct, classroom and school regulations, and how to abide by them (Cotton, 2015). An organization without policy is an organization without control (Ulla, 2018).

However, there are also not a few students who violate the rules that have been made. Students who commit violations must be held responsible for their actions. Schools have their respective policies for acting against their students. However, because it is accomplished manually rather than centrally, recording offenses presents challenges for a review. When you want to recapitulate the administration, you will check many books listing violations that take a long time. Manually recording violations also has problems with the appropriateness of writing violations. Given the challenges of manually documenting and summarizing violations and identifying every student, an accessible note-taking system is required (Arisandi et al., 2021). For school policies to be effective, they must be more than just statements on paper (Forstall, 2019).

The Student Discipline Unit of the St. Dominic College of Asia uses violation slips for recording offenses committed by the college students. From then on, all the collected violation slips are manually inputted into a Microsoft Excel file for record-keeping. At the end of each semester, the student discipline officer must switch through worksheets one by one to look for a specific record. If any offenses are found for a specific student, a piece of paper containing the written applied corresponding sanctions will be attached to the clearance form for the student to complete before signing the clearance. This manual process of recording violations, managing recorded offenses, and applying corresponding sanctions is inconvenient.

Managing by hand is a highly difficult and time-consuming procedure. Handling each document and storing it safely is not easy (Haas et al., 2021). It takes more effort and physical space to keep track of paper documents, find information, and keep details secure. A manual transaction frequently needs to be completed entirely rather than simply updated when errors are made, or adjustments are required. With manual or partially automated systems, information often must be written down and copied or entered more than once (Breitmeyer, 2015). A manual system is a bookkeeping system where records are maintained by hand without using a computer system (Slyngstad & Helgheim, 2022). Manual document filing means you are placing faith in the people handling the files. They can be lost, damaged, or misplaced in a variety of ways. Important client data could be lost in a fire or other natural disaster. You will have to start over at square one, getting the information back (Bowers, 2017).

On the other hand, a document management system lets you consolidate core business information into a central location and make it available whenever and wherever you are. Time is on your side (Barnum, 2018). Going electronic saves companies time and money (Burton, n.d.). Electronic records management (ERM) is the management of electronic files and documents as records (Garland, 2019). A computerized system's benefits include quicker and more effective record-keeping. This means you would not have to spend hours preparing these documents manually (Picincu, 2020).

The development of this project in a web-based nature using the Laravel Framework would serve as an alternative solution for the manual recording of offenses on and off-campus, monitoring and managing recorded violations, and applying corresponding sanctions with ease and accuracy of the information. Web-based applications are dynamic websites programmed on the server and delivered to the client through a browser (Dissanayake & Dias, 2017). Web-based programs offer numerous commercial benefits over desktop programs. These applications can be accessed from any computer through the internet, instead of having to be individually installed on each computer that you wish to access them from (Khamooshi, 2019). Furthermore, you can access your data instantly. That is because it is stored in a central cloud-based location, not on individual workstations, hard drives, or a network of physical servers (Peerman, 2019).

The Student Discipline Unit of St. Dominic College of Asia uses violation slip forms to record offenses committed by its college students. Written information is not always a reliable piece of evidence since students may alter identities; hence, manually inputting all the recorded offenses into the Microsoft Excel file would also not always be efficient due to inaccurate information. The student discipline officer will not know who recorded the offenses, and students are not always notified of the recorded offenses. Students will only know the degree and number of committed offenses every end of the semester before the signing of clearance, and only then will they know the applied corresponding sanctions that need to be completed, which is very inconvenient. Violations committed inside the campus are not observed and recorded since the recording of offenses only takes place at the school's main entrance and exit gates.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the institution has set policies regarding online classes, which will not be recorded because the violation slip form will be unavailable as well. Addressing this problem will have practical benefits to the institution in the execution and implementation of its policies, rules, and regulations to maintain student decorum, peace, order, safety, and security of the students on and off-campus, from face-to-face classes to online classes.

Objectives of the Study

The study's objective is to develop a student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia in a web-based nature. The study specifically aims to:

1. Plan the flow of the project and regulate possible solutions to improve the processes involved in the previously proposed system.
2. Gather all the needed information and analyze the requirements for the design, development, and execution of the web-based student violation management system.
3. Design and develop appropriate functions, modules, and sub-modules that will serve as an alternative solution for the manual processing of recording and managing violations committed by the college students and application of corresponding sanctions.
4. Test and evaluate the system using the ISO 9126 International Standards to ensure that the project meets the requirements in the context of functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability before the deployment and implementation.
5. Provide a trusted, fully functional, and responsive web-based student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia.

Methodology

System Development Approach

The Agile Development Methodology by Martin Fowler is the basis for the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) of the project. Distinct phases involved in the Agile Methodology are approaches for the step-by-step process for developing the web-based student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia.

Figure 1. Agile Model by Martin Fowler for SVMS' System Paradigm

Planning Phase. The first phase of Agile methodology is the planning phase, which focuses on determining what to develop and how to start the process by constructing ideas to create a clear picture of the project vision. The researchers came up with the idea to develop a web-based system as an alternative solution for the manual process of recording offenses committed by college students, monitoring records, and applying corresponding sanctions. Thus, the researchers started the planning phase by conducting a series of informational interviews and observations to determine the problems and issues faced by the institution and provide IT-based solutions.

Requirements Analysis Phase. The second phase of Agile methodology is to gather all the needed information by collaborating with the client to have a sensible objective to meet the user's expectations and requirements. With all the information and requirements gathered from the planning phase, the researchers have concluded to use Laravel and Bootstrap Frameworks as the structure for building the project in a web-based nature for ease of access and control.

Design Phase. The third phase of Agile methodology is understanding the logical and physical designs of the project's system. To better interpret the processes involved and validate the architectural design of the project, the researchers designed standard diagrams based on the Unified Modeling Language (UML) such as Context Flow Diagram (CFD) for the overview of users interactions, the Data Flow Diagram (DFD) to categorize the levels of users interactions between the processes of the system modules, the Sequence Diagram to discern the processes of users interactions in time sequence, the Entity Relationship Diagram (ERD) and Class Diagram to show the logical structure and relationships of the system's data, classes, and operational functions, and the Network Architecture to indicate the organization and configuration of required physical components for the execution of the project.

Development Phase. The fourth phase of Agile methodology is to develop the web-based system following the client's expectations and requirements. The developer started converting prototypes and wireframes into codes with guidance from the diagrams created in the design phase. The system developed in a web nature is suitable for various device platforms and browsers for ease of access and control and delivers a better user experience.

Quality Assurance and Testing Phase. The fifth phase of Agile methodology is to perform a series of tests and documentation of results to resolve any flaws, errors, and bugs to improve and enhance the system processes. The quality assurance and testing phase focuses on maintaining the integrity of the system to ensure the delivery of the high-quality solution and guarantee its working state for the implementation phase.

Implementation Phase. The sixth phase of Agile methodology is to present the fully functional web-based student violation management system, evaluated and approved by the end-users and expert-users for utilization, and will serve as an alternative solution for the problems and issues faced by the institution regarding the implementation of recording and monitoring violations committed by the students.

Track and Monitor Phase. The seventh and last phase of Agile methodology is monitoring the working state of the implemented system to determine possible functions and modules to add for future updates and enhancements.

Use Case Diagram

Figure 2 shows the possible interactions of registered users with the system where the modules and sub-modules can be accessed based on the assigned role. College students, on the other hand, cannot access the system but only receive email notifications and digital or printed copies of the report regarding the committed offenses.

Figure 2. Use Case Diagram for SVMS

Sequence Diagram

Figure 3 depicts the scenarios of user interactions within the modules and sub-modules of the system in sequential order. The system always verifies if the user’s assigned role has permission to access specific modules and sub-modules.

Figure 3. Sequence Diagram for SVMS

Context Flow Diagram (CFD)

Figure 4 shows level 0 or the general flow of relationships that the system has with the system administrator and the registered users. The system administrator has full access and control to all the modules and sub-modules of the system, while registered users have only limited access controls based on the assigned role.

Figure 4. Context Flow Diagram for SVMS

Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

Figures 5 and 6 map the flow of data for specific processes across the modules and sub-modules of the system. These figures illustrate level 0, or the general flow and relationship of the system administrator and the registered users with the system. The researchers used the term “system users” to unify registered users and the system administrator, as their access differs only based on the assigned role. Each data flow diagram shows the processes involved per module and sub-module.

Figure 5. Data Flow Diagram for SVMS System Administrator

Figure 6. Data Flow Diagram for SVMS Registered Users (Non-Administrator Users)

Statistical Treatment of Data

The mean is the sum of all the scores divided by the number of respondents. The formula is population is equal to ΣX over the number of scores. If the scores are from a sample, then the population refers to the mean. Meanwhile, the reliability statistics of the gathered data were used with the Cronbach’s alpha rules, containing 30 items or questions. The formula used is $(N \times C) / v + (N-1) \times C$, where N is the number of items, C is the average covariance, and v is the average variance of the data. Based on the standardized items, the result of the Cronbach’s alpha is 0.9443, resulting in the remarks of "excellent," suggesting that there is strong internal consistency and reliability among the thirty-focused items.

Results and Discussion

Level of Satisfaction

The researchers used a five-point scale as the basis for the system's level of satisfaction in terms of functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability based on the respondents' evaluation and feedback.

Table 1 shows the rate and interpretation of the five-point scale, which indicates whether the system’s level of satisfaction is acceptable, needs improvement, or is not acceptable. As such, the overall rating of the development of a web-based student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia is expected to be 2.51 or higher, considering these are the values indicating the project is feasible.

Table 1. Level of Satisfaction

Scale	Range of Menu Value	Qualitative Information
5	4.51 – 5.00	Highly Acceptable
4	3.51 – 4.50	Moderately Acceptable
3	2.51 – 3.50	Acceptable
2	1.51 – 2.50	Needs Improvement
1	1.00 – 1.50	Not Acceptable

Respondent Distribution

The respondents are the employees from the Departments of Student Affairs and Services, the Student Discipline Unit, and the ICT Department. Table 2 indicates that 40 percent of the respondents are end-users, and the remaining 60 percent are expert-users.

Table 2. Count of Respondents (n=8)

Respondent	Frequency	Percentage
End-Users	3	40%
Expert-Users	5	60%

Overall Level of Satisfaction Based on the Respondents' Distribution

Table 3 shows the overall response of the expert users and end-users using the levels of satisfaction and respondent frequency. The system's functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability have consistently obtained highly acceptable remarks, with an average rating of 4.81 from the responses of the expert users and 4.83 from the end-users, resulting in an overall rating of 4.82, indicating the system is highly acceptable.

Table 3. Overall Level of Satisfaction Based on the Respondents' Distribution

Category	Expert User	End User	Overall Level of Satisfaction	Rating
Functionality	4.46	4.49	4.48	Highly Acceptable
Reliability	4.45	4.34	4.40	Highly Acceptable
Usability	4.48	4.46	4.47	Highly Acceptable
Efficiency	4.52	4.46	4.49	Highly Acceptable
Maintainability	4.51	4.38	4.44	Highly Acceptable
Portability	4.47	4.48	4.47	Highly Acceptable
Average	4.48	4.43	4.46	Highly Acceptable

The overall functionality of the system has been highly acceptable in terms of the accuracy of expected results, the suitability of operations for specified tasks, the interoperability of shared information, the security to account accessibility, and the functionality compliance for tracking records. Reliability has been highly acceptable of the system to inform system users of invalid requests, its capability to process data recoveries, its behavior in response to errors, its stability of operations, and its capability to handle requests from multiple users.

The overall usability of the system has been highly acceptable to present instructions in operating its modules and sub-modules, its ease of use and access, its efficiency to various web browsers, its user-friendliness to standard and non-standard users, and its readiness to operate. The efficiency has been highly acceptable from loading requests, its productivity, its capability to perform required tasks, its capability to meet users' expectations to generate results, and its acceptable latency to process operations.

The overall maintainability of the system has been highly acceptable from analyzing the degree of errors, its capability to handle dynamic changes made by the system users, its stability during modification, its level of effectiveness when in use, and its level of maintaining the states of data during modifications. The portability of the system has been highly acceptable from its adaptability to various device screen sizes, its accessibility to different web browsers, its capability to operate under different device platforms, its capability to access and retrieve data, and its capability to handle multiple users.

This result agrees with Danlog et al. (2017), as it provides efficient and accurate recording of records, to maintain and secure the student's records and easy retrieval of student records, and to lessen the workload of the staff. In addition, a web-based system is needed that can take notes easily to ease the manual recording and recapitulating violations and to lessen the difficulty of recognizing all students (Arisandi et al., 2021).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The researchers were suitable to develop a web-based student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia using version 8 of the Laravel Framework, which will serve as an alternative solution for the manual processing of recording violations committed by the college student, monitoring and managing recorded offenses, and application of corresponding sanctions. The results obtained from the evaluation responses of eight respondents, three of whom are end-users and the remaining five are expert users, and the results of the reliability statistics using the Cronbach's alpha test show that the consistency of the data proves the developed project meets the standard expectations of the users.

Thus, the researchers conclude that after thorough planning, analysis, development, and quality testing, the study resolved the following issues: the Student Discipline Unit will no longer have to provide and use violation slip forms for recording violations, which is not always a piece of substantial evidence as violators may alter their information, such as names or student numbers, to avoid punishments. Looking for specific records can be done easily and quickly using the filter options and search fields provided by the system instead of switching through Microsoft Excel's worksheets one by one. Violators will be instantly and well informed regarding the committed offenses and the applied corresponding sanctions due to the capability of the system to send email notifications and generate pdf copies of reports.

The student discipline officer and the violators can know who is responsible for recording offenses. The recording of committed violations can be done on or off the campus because the system is suitable for any form of the learning environment, from face-to-face to online classes. When it comes to signing of clearance, the student discipline officer can effortlessly know if the violator has observed and completed the applied corresponding sanctions because the system can determine whether the recorded offenses have been cleared or if there are applied sanctions. Since the system is developed in a web-based nature, system users can easily access the system using various device platforms.

The overall level of satisfaction in the context of functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability of the system is considered highly acceptable, according to results obtained from the responses of specific respondents using ISO 9126 as the basis for the evaluation tool. Therefore, the project is fit for deployment and implementation.

Recommendations

The development of a web-based student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia should accomplish and support the requirements of the Student Discipline Unit and the Department of Student Affairs and Services for the execution and implementation of the general policies, guidelines, rules, and regulations of the St. Dominic College of Asia.

Since the research is progressing, the development of a web-based student violation management system for St. Dominic College of Asia must be capable of providing more extensive data analytics of recorded offenses; being fully responsive to various screen size ratios; organizing all the recorded offenses on a per-semester basis; generating an Excel file format of recorded offenses for access and shared of information; providing a messaging module that allows the system users to communicate with each other using the system; and utilizing the SDCA's student portal as an extension that will help the college student or the violator to keep track of all the committed offenses and the applied corresponding sanctions.

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